

The electric charge (2.0)

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In physics most phenomena in the microcosm have some kind of an explanatory description. But at the smallest scale size there exists no description of an underlying “tangible” explanatory structure. That is why the description of the origin of the electric charge is more or less limited to a link to particles that carry the electric charge.

Introduction

[Coulomb’s inverse-square law](#) shows a remarkable resemblance with the [inverse-square law of universal gravitation](#). Unfortunately the model of Newtonian gravity is derived with the help of the phenomenological point of view (the mutual relation between matter objects). Figure 1 shows the same Newtonian gravity but now as a vector influence in vacuum space by the basic quantum fields (QFT) around matter objects.^[1] The reasoning is simple, different vector fields can be merged but multiple scalar fields or multiple 3D topological fields do not exist at the smallest scale size.

figure 1

There is an important difference between the [electric charge](#) and the gravitational force. Particles with opposite electric charges attract each other and particles with the same electric charge repel each other. The electric charge has no known underlying mechanism. Therefore it is reasonable to search for the origin of the electric charge with the help of the model of quantised space.

References:

1. Art Hobson (2013); "There are no particles, there are only fields". American journal of physics 81, 211. DOI: 10.1119/1.4789885. <https://arxiv.org/ftp/arxiv/papers/1204/1204.4616.pdf>

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Matter and anti-matter

The negative electric charge of an electron ($-e$) is the opposite of the electric charge of the positron ($+e$). Like the proton ($+e$) and anti-proton ($-e$) have opposite electric charges. It is clear that anti-matter cannot be a local deficit of energy as the opposite of a local surplus of energy (e.g. a proton). Matter and anti-matter – e.g. the proton and the anti-proton – annihilate each other and the result is free energy (a couple of high energy photons).

A proton and an anti-proton have the same rest mass so there is no difference between the dipole of a proton and the dipole of an anti-proton.^[2] Experiments have showed that matter and anti-matter “feel” the same influence by the force of gravity.^[3] The only difference between a particle and its anti-particle is the direction of the spin. Because the spin and opposite spin explains the annihilation of a particle and its anti-particle.

figure 2

The constant velocity of the propagation of the quantum of energy is the speed of light. The scalar mechanism of every unit of quantised space^[4] creates local concentrations of energy (topological deformation). The result is drawn in the schematic figure 2. The arrows show the direction of the resultant propagation during the concentration of energy by the units of quantised space (drawn as cubes).

figure 3

If figure 2 shows the origin of the concentration of energy (mass), its mirror image will show the creation of anti-mass (figure 3). Combining figure 2 and figure 3 will annihilate both configurations and the remaining local surplus of energy will be emitted immediately by an even number of (high energy) photons.

In other words, it is reasonable to suppose that the positive and negative electric charges have a direct relation with the direction of the rotation of local concentrations of energy (like protons, electrons, their anti-particles and vacuum space around).

References:

2. S.E. Grimm (2025); “*The dipole in quantised space*”
DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14630170
<https://zenodo.org/record/14630170>
3. E.K. Anderson et al. (2023); “*Observation of the effect of gravity on the motion of anti-matter*”
Nature 621, 716-722
<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-023-06527-1>
4. S.E. Grimm (2024); “*On the geometrical structure of quantised space*”
DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14556269
<https://zenodo.org/record/14556269>

Vectors

The existence of a local concentration of energy (mass) is not the same as a local amplitude of the universal electric field. A local amplitude in vacuum space represents not only a surplus of energy but also corresponding vectors that reflect the amount of concentrated energy. In a universe without matter every quantum of energy generates corresponding magnetic field vectors. However, the creation of a rest mass carrying particle is impossible without one or more decreased scalars of the Higgs field. A decreased scalar has no points of contact with the adjacent

scalars around and the consequence is the vectorisation of the flat Higgs field around the decreased scalar(s). The vectorisation is drawn in figure 4 with the help of resultant vectors (red arrows). The red scalar in the centre of the proton has no points of contact with the scalars (not drawn) of the adjacent (schematic) units around.^[4]

figure 4

If there is no decreased scalar there is no vectorised vacuum space around (red arrows) and no increasing “energy density” towards the particle (grey rasterised concentric shells). That means that the scalar in the centre of the image mediates the vectors of the magnetic field. Vectors that are determined by the local energy density. Of course there is somewhere compensation for “missing” vectors because of the universal conservation of energy and corresponding vectors.

Figure 2 and 3 show the concentration of energy – topological deformation – by a number of units. Every unit has exactly the same internal spherical shape forming mechanism (scalar mechanism that creates geometrical change) and every unit deforms at exactly the same amount of deformation at exactly the same moment. Just because the volume of every unit is invariant.^[4]

The unit in the centre of figure 4 is the unit with the highest amount of topological deformation. Every unit in the universe transforms its shape with the same amount of topological deformation during the same amount of time. The consequence is that the unit in the centre determines the velocity of the whole geometrical configuration from the position of 1 unit to the position of the adjacent unit. The units itself don’t move, because it is the rest frame. It is the topological deformation that is pushed by all the involved units to the new position.

Without matter the universe is one enormous volume with different amplitudes of topological deformation. But now there is matter and the geometrical configuration in figure 4 is in motion in relation to the rest frame (the units). It is the decreased scalar and the related vectorisation of the flat Higgs field (red arrows) that keeps the overall shape of the geometrical configuration intact. Inclusive the increasing deformation of the universal electric field towards the particle (grey rasterised concentric shells in figure 4).

figure 5

The same rasterised concentric shells are visible in figure 5 but now the image shows the magnetic dipole (vectors) that is generated by the motion of the particle in relation to the rest frame.^[2] Every motion of matter generates a dipole. Even a geometrical configuration of clusters of galaxies that move in the same direction (see large image below).^[5]

figure 6

I can combine figure 4 and 5 because the magnetic dipole (5) and the vectorised Higgs field (4) are manifestations of the existence of the particle. The resulting geometrical configuration is drawn in figure 6. The particle moves upwards because the point of view is from aside. In other words the horizontal disk of red arrows around the particle – actually the transition zone of the dipole – is the region where the electron of a Hydrogen atom resides.

However, the velocity of the whole geometrical configuration is much slower than the resultant propagation of the energy in vacuum space around.^[6] The consequence is that the velocity of the electron – a concentration of energy too – must correspond with the resultant velocity of the involved units. In other words, somewhere at a certain distance

from the particle – see the red circle in figure 7 – the free energy of the “loop” concentrates itself and the velocity of the created amount of mass corresponds with the velocity of the resulting motion of the free energy of the disk at that specific distance from the particle.

figure 7

If an unstable nucleus ejects a neutron, the particle will “decay” into a proton, an electron and an anti-neutrino in about 14 minutes. But it is clear that the mass of the electron doesn’t originate from the mass of the neutron.

Reference:

5. Yehuda Hoffman et al. (2017); “*The dipole repeller*” Nature Astronomy 1, art. 0036
<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41550-016-0036>
<https://arxiv.org/abs/1702.02483>
6. S.E. Grimm (2024); “*On resultant motion in discrete space*” <https://zenodo.org/record/11193931>

The electric charge

Suppose that 2 geometrical configurations – like the configuration of a proton in figure 6 – approach each other. Each configuration represents a balanced asymmetrical energy distribution. That means that each configuration will not adopt free energy from the units near to the boundary to increase the mass of the particle.

Figure 1 shows how the vectors of the vectorised Higgs field from vacuum space around create an “attracting” force between matter objects. But the involved units in vacuum space in between 2 protons that approach each other will create a resistance in the opposite direction. And the vectors of the dipole will do the same. So equal “charges” will repel each other.

The geometrical configuration of a Hydrogen atom (+e) without electron has an energy shortage. So it is obvious that there is a resultant force that couples a positive charged particle (+e) with a negative charged particle (-e).

But the situation gets a bit confusing if an positron (anti-electron) has a positive charge (+e) and an anti-proton a negative charge (-e). Because the difference between a particle and its anti-particle is the direction of its spin and the direction of the motion of free energy in vacuum space around the particle. So why generates an opposite direction of spin and corresponding motion of free energy around an opposite electric charge?

If an electron and a positron approach each other the topological deformation of the units in vacuum space in between both particles will annihilate each other topological deformation too. So we get the situation in figure 1. An “attracting” force.

Non-locality

All the vectors in the universe that are generated by the energy “transfer” of the universal electric field are conserved. That means that vacuum space everywhere in the universe is pervaded by vectors that act instantaneous.

Figure 1 of reference 7 shows 4 possibilities (A, B, C and D) to interpret the nature of reality. Possibility C seems quite meaningless till we realise that possibility C shows in a schematic way all the vectors in vacuum space. And these vectors are conserved because of the conservation of energy.

In other words, there exists an instantaneous influence that determines all the geometrical configurations in the universe in direct relation with the energy distribution everywhere in the universe. The consequence is that in practise it is impossible to describe “what is going on” in quantised space in a really accurate way. That is why the phenomenological point of view to describe the different transformations is sometimes the only way to create some clarity.

References:

7. S.E. Grimm (2024); “*The box without walls*” <https://zenodo.org/record/14540104>